

Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2026; Issue #01 – Year in Review:

Commentary on Pawliuk, C. et al.

Colleen Pawliuk, MLIS

Research Librarian, BC Children's Hospital Research Institute, British Columbia, Canada

Email: cpawliuk@bcchr.ca

And

Candice Barrans, Parent Partner

Parent Partner - BC Children's Hospital Research Institute, British Columbia, Canada

Email: Candice.Barrans@bcchr.ca

Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2026 blog post by Pawliuk, C. et al., TRENDS in Pediatric Palliative Care Research – Visuals and Analysis of Trends in 2025, published at Pediatricpalliative.com.

This commentary is a part of the Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research commentary series. To learn more or to sign up for our monthly newsletter visit:

<https://pediatricpalliative.com/research-blog/>

TRENDS features articles relevant to the pediatric palliative care – showcasing current trends in the research. Each issue includes a personal analysis of the impacts of that research, written by experts in the field. Once a year, we look back at the literature and highlight top performers and connections from the past year. Welcome to our 2025 publication review of pediatric palliative care (PPC) research published in TRENDS.

This year the top three leading journals PPC research are *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management (JPSM)*, *Children* and *BMC Palliative Care*. The latter two journals, which published a total of 33 articles from our list, are both gold open access journals. As we support empowerment of researchers and practitioners in low-resource settings, patient advocacy groups and patients/parents in research, moves toward open access are critical.

The 2025 top three authors in the PPC field were Justin Baker, Lorna Fraser, and Julia Downing, with 11 or more publications each. We are excited to report that Julia Downing has agreed to write our Low Resource setting Special edition, to be published at the end of 2026. Be sure to catch her issue later this year. Additionally, we have included visualizations of the networks of co-authors and their organizations or institutions to offer opportunities to build new bridges or leverage current relationships. A visualization of the top funders for PPC research aims to highlight potential opportunities for funding.

To show emerging themes in our list we have a visualization of the indexed terms (subject headings) assigned to each of our articles. We present these indexed terms for each article as a

network map to both show more terms and to show the relationships between the themes.

TRENDS newsletter in 2025 saw a year of growth. We connected with 132 new subscribers, we redesigned our newsletter and website and moved our citation library to Zotero. In 2026, while we will continue to publish 10 monthly newsletters and 4 special editions, we will also be working to support our users to better use our resources.

TRENDS seeks to improve access for and collaboration with our global readership of clinicians, researchers, nurses, social workers, parents, students, and support staff. We thank you for reading, contributing to, and sharing our newsletter. TRENDS wants to thank you for the passion from which you care for your patients, families, communities, colleagues, and trainees. We hope our newsletter continues to inform, support, and inspire your journey.

- The team at Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research Newsletter

To view all the visualizations full screen and in their interactive formats, visit the blog post of this report click [here](#).

TRENDS in Pediatric Palliative Care Research – Visuals and Analysis of Trends in 2025

By: Colleen Pawliuk, Research Librarian & Candice Barrans, Parent Partner

Methods

All the [papers included in our 2025 lists](#), including special editions (n=453), were found in Scopus. Papers that were not indexed in Scopus could not be retrieved (n=63), and so we were left with a total of 390 papers for this analysis. [VOSviewer](#) was used to create the citation network visualizations and [Tableau Public](#) was used to create all other visualizations.

Top Journals

All journals with 4 or more papers on our 2025 list are included in this visualization and the 2024 Journal Impact Factor (JIF) is used to show journal metrics. To see the full information for all journals you can view the visualization full-screen.

Top Authors

The authors with 4 or more papers on our 2023 lists were:

JN Baker - 12 Papers	PS Hinds - 6 Papers	JW Mack - 5 Papers
LK Fraser - 12 Papers	MC Kars - 6 Papers	FEM Murtagh - 5 Papers
J Downing - 11 Papers	EC Kaye - 6 Papers	S Oddie - 5 Papers
F Benini - 9 Papers	B Phillips - 6 Papers	JM Snaman - 5 Papers
J Hackett - 7 Papers	C Delgado-Corcoran - 5 Papers	G Subramanian - 5 Papers
J Noyes - 7 Papers	R Harding - 5 Papers	C Vasudevan - 5 Papers
J Wolfe - 7 Papers	A Haynes - 5 Papers	H Weatherly - 5 Papers
S Friebert - 6 Papers	S Hinde - 5 Papers	A Zanin - 5 Papers
R Hain - 6 Papers		

Top Funders

Below are the top funding organizations for 2023 that have funded 4 or more studies on our list.

Co-Authorship Networks

All authors with 1) two or more publications on our list, and; 2) one or more co-author links are included in this visualization of co-authorship.

Organizational Networks

This visualization shows the organizations of the authors contributing to research in the field and the networks between them. To be included in this visualization an organization must appear at least twice.

